

LEGAL REGULATION OF ISLAMIC INSURANCE: TAKOFUL

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Annotation: *The concept of takaful originated from individual common interests in the industrial era of the early 1900s. Of the 2.5 billion poor in the world, only eighty million are now covered by some form of micro-insurance. In India and China, only 3 per cent of the poor are insured, while only 0.3 per cent of the poor in Africa are insured. In 23 of the world's 100 poorest countries, microinsurance is currently undefined. The main part of the population is in the poor. Moreover, the public's awareness of the importance of insurance is much lower. This article still emphasizes the need to focus efforts on training in Islamic insurance to understand the protective aspects that insurance can provide to the population. Traditional insurance includes elements of uncertainty, gambling, and interest, all of which cannot be accepted in Islamic law. There were concerns among Muslims that traditional banking and insurance were not in line with Islamic law. This has enabled 1.6 billion Muslims around the world to create a new industry - takaful - that offers products of protection and saving from dangers. One of the biggest problems facing the takaful industry is the misconception that it is only for Muslims. Despite religious and cultural differences, takaful products have attracted even non-Muslim communities. However, the interest shown by non-Muslims and the support of Muslims is not enough to raise and develop awareness of takaful and what it offers. It is this lack of awareness that poses one of the biggest challenges for the development and growth of national and global industries.*

Keywords: *Takoful, insurance, kalfol, traditional insurance, gambling, interest.*

ПРАВОВОЕ РЕГУЛИРОВАНИЕ ИСЛАМСКОГО СТРАХОВАНИЯ: ТАКОФУЛА

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Аннотация: *Концепция такафул возникла из индивидуальных общих интересов в индустриальную эпоху начала 1900-х годов. Из 2,5 миллиардов*

бедняков в мире только 80 миллионов в настоящее время застрахованы в той или иной форме микрострахования. В Индии и Китае застраховано лишь 3 процента бедняков, а в Африке застраховано лишь 0,3 процента бедняков. В 23 из 100 беднейших стран мира микрострахование в настоящее время не выявлено. Основная часть населения находится в бедности. Более того, информированность населения о важности страхования значительно ниже. В этой статье по-прежнему подчеркивается необходимость сосредоточить усилия на обучении исламскому страхованию, чтобы понять защитные аспекты, которые страхование может предоставить населению. Традиционное страхование включает в себя элементы неопределенности, азартных игр и процентов, которые не могут быть приняты в исламском праве. Мусульмане опасались, что традиционное банковское дело и страхование не соответствуют исламскому праву. Это позволило 1,6 миллиардам мусульман по всему миру создать новую отрасль, предлагающую продукты защиты и сбережения – такафул. Одной из самых больших проблем, с которыми сталкивается такафул-индустрия, является неправильное представление о том, что она предназначена только для мусульман. Несмотря на религиозные и культурные различия, продукты такафул привлекают даже немусульманские общины. Однако интерес, проявленный немусульманами, и поддержка мусульман недостаточны для повышения и развития осведомленности о такафуле и о том, что он предлагает. Именно это отсутствие осведомленности создает одну из самых больших проблем для развития и роста национальной и глобальной промышленности.

Ключевые слова: *такофул, страхование, калфол, традиционное страхование, азартные игры, проценты.*

Islamic insurance can take many forms, including takaful, waqf, mutual aid funds, and mutual insurance. If we consider takoful, which is the basis of Islamic insurance, "takaful" is an Arabic word meaning "mutual guarantee" and provided for in the legislation of Uzbekistan, citizens and organizations. by merging certain funds by, is compatible with the possible bilateral insurance. This type of insurance is also used in some countries as a foundation. From this we can understand the importance of paying attention not only to the name of the financial product or system, but also to its form and principles.

In the process of covering this article, the logical, historical, methods of consistency and objectivity were widely used. This article describes the constructive stages of the introduction of takoful as a new financial instrument, reflecting the priorities based on advanced foreign experience; Taking into account the genesis, conceptual principles, typology of the economic category of "takoful", it is proposed to define this instrument as a separate type of security, unlike ordinary shares and bonds; based on the positive impact of taco development on the economy through competition between financial sectors and the transformation of unused funds into investment; It is proposed to use the takoful instrument in Uzbekistan on the principles of musharaka, mudoraba, murobaha, salam, exception and lease agreements, by disclosing the nature of the risk, the interest in the benefits of the activity and the interests of the majority over the interests of one person.

Insurance is one of the most important elements of the country's financial system. The presence of the elements of usury (interest), decision (uncertainty), and gambling (gambling) in the traditional insurance system of many countries, including our country, does not correspond to the religious beliefs of Muslims.

It is difficult to determine the exact origin of insurance in Islam. Today, however, given the nature of the insurance contract, it can be said that insurance transactions have been in place since the time of the Holy Prophet Muhammad (pbuh). Ibn Abidin (1784-1836), a nineteenth-century Hanafi jurist who was the first to develop insurance in the Muslim world, was the first to advance the concept of insurance.⁵⁶

A special insurance fund will be set up to ensure that the takaful is carried out properly. The members of the Fund, in accordance with the previously announced procedure, make contributions to the Fund as insurance contributions, and the Fund covers the agreed losses of its members at the expense of these funds, which become its property. . At the end of the year, part of the excess funds from the insurance will be withdrawn or distributed among the members in accordance with the rules of the company's charter, and the rest of the fund in the form of a foundation will be provided to the needy. possible.

All human activity is at risk of loss due to unforeseen events. To alleviate this burden for individuals, what we now call insurance has existed for at least 215 BC. This concept has been used in various forms for over 1,400 years. It is derived from the Arabic word "kafala", which means "mutual guarantee" or "joint guarantee". The

⁵⁶ E.A. Baydaulet. "Islom moliya asoslari", "O'zbekiston" Toshkent 2019y. 7-bet.

concept is based on the principles of compensation and the division of responsibilities between society.

Takoful emerged in the ancient Arab tribes as a general responsibility that imposed on those who committed crimes against other members of the tribe the obligation to compensate the victims or their heirs. The principle later applied to many aspects of life, including maritime trade, with participants contributing to the fund to cover anyone who had an accident on a group voyage.

In modern traditional insurance, the insurance seller (insurance company) sells the policies and invests the proceeds for the benefit of its shareholders. So there is a clear difference between insurers and shareholders. Payments to insurers may vary depending on financial performance, but the minimum positive return is always guaranteed in the contract.

Takoful is commonly referred to as Islamic insurance; This is due to the apparent similarity between the guarantee contract and the insurance contract. However, takaful is based on the principle of cooperatives and the principle of division between the funds and operations of shareholders, so that the ownership of takaful (insurance) funds and operations passes to the insured. Muslim jurists conclude that in Islam, insurance should be based on the principles of reciprocity and cooperation, which include elements of common responsibility, common compensation, common interest and solidarity.

In Takaful, the insurers are joint investors with the insurance seller (takaful operator), who act as a manager or business agent for the insurers . Owners of insurance policies share in the benefits of the investment money, as well as in its losses. Positive policy returns are not legally guaranteed, as any fixed profit guarantee is like taking interest and violating the interest rate ban. For some time, traditional insurance has been considered unconstitutional, which prohibits excessive uncertainty in circulation and investment in interest-bearing assets; both are factors inherent in the traditional insurance business.

However, takaful is in accordance with the Shari'ah (which defines the principles of compensation and general responsibility between society) and has been approved by Muslim scholars. There are now general, health and family (life) takaful plans for Muslim communities. Islamic insurance is governed by specific Islamic norms:

Garar - There is a decision in the insurance contract, because if it is not claimed, one party (insurance company) can receive all the benefits (insurance company), and the other party (participant) can not receive any benefits. Ibn Taymiyyah, a leading Muslim scholar, argued that "the ruling found in the treaty

existed because one party benefited and the other party did not." Prohibition of the decision requires the eventual distribution of all investment income and losses in order to avoid excessive uncertainty over the insurer's investment income.⁵⁷

Maysir - Islamic scholars have argued that maysir (gambling) and decision are interrelated. Where there are elements of decision, there are usually elements of greed. When Maysir is in the insurance contract; the policyholder pays a small premium in the hopes of earning a larger amount; in the event of an insured event, the insurer loses the amount paid for the insurance premium; If the claims are higher than the amount contributed by the policy owners, the company will be in bankruptcy.⁵⁸

Interest is a traditional foundation insurance policy that promises a guaranteed payment under a contract, thus violating the interest rate ban. The Riba element also exists in favor of investments used by traditional insurance companies to pay off policyholders' claims. This is because most insurance funds are invested by them in financial instruments such as bonds and stocks that may contain interest elements.

Gambling and insurance are two different types of transactions. Gambling is speculative in assessing risk, while insurance is pure risk and not speculative. Gambling can create this risk and win or lose. There is already a risk in insurance and it will try to minimize the financial consequences of that risk. Insurance transfers the effects of this risk to someone else and saves a person from danger. Nevertheless, the danger remains.

If gambling causes discord, destruction and hatred, insurance based on the principles of partnership allows the insured person to reduce the financial impact, in which case it leads to poverty of the person and his dependents and thus their place in society can weaken. There is nothing in Islam that prevents people from providing for their dependents. General insurance for large groups of the insured strengthens the financial base of society.

Islamic scholar Yusuf Ali, in his translation of the Holy Qur'an, comments on Surat al-Baqara, verse 219: large-scale statistics are simply deleted. Insurers are rewarded in proportion to the risks, accurately and scientifically calculated.⁵⁹

Islamic insurance requires each participant to contribute to a fund used to support each other, with each participant allocating sufficient funds to cover the expected claims. The basic principles of takoful can be summarized as follows:

⁵⁷ B. Jurayev. (tarj) "Islomiy moliya va bank tizimi", "O'zbekiston" Toshkent 2019y. 138-bet

⁵⁸ B. Jurayev. (tarj) "Islomiy moliya va bank tizimi", "O'zbekiston" Toshkent 2019y. 138-bet

⁵⁹ B. Jurayev. (tarj) "Islomiy moliya va bank tizimi", "O'zbekiston" Toshkent 2019y. 139-bet

Policy holders work together for the common good. Each insurer pays a portion of the premium as a charity to help those in need.

Losses are divided and liabilities are distributed according to the system of social cohesion. Uncertainty over subscriptions and compensation is eliminated. He does not seek to benefit others. Theoretically, Takaful is considered to be cooperative insurance, where members contribute a certain amount of money to the common pool. The purpose of this system is not to benefit, but to support the principle of “lift each other’s burden”.

One of the best ways to reduce the risk of accidents in today's business is to take out insurance. The concept of insurance, where resources are combined to help the needy, is not at all contrary to Islamic principles. There are three important differences between traditional insurance and takaful:

Traditional insurance includes elements of extreme uncertainty (decision) in the insurance contract;

Gambling (interest) Interest in the investment activities of traditional insurance companies (riba) as a consequence of excessive uncertainty based on future results;

Traditional insurance companies are driven by a desire to make a profit for shareholders; The traditional insurance system can be exploited. For example, a company can receive a high reward (especially in monopolistic situations) with the full benefit of such surplus prices.⁶⁰

The main difference between takoful and traditional insurance is in the method of risk assessment and management, as well as in the management of the Takaful fund. Additional differences also exist in the relationship between the operator (in terms of traditional insurance: using the term insurer) and the participants (usually the insured or the insured). Takoful business is also different from traditional insurance, in which the shareholders, not the shareholders, use only the profits from Takaful and investment assets. How the takaful works All participants (policyholders) agree to guarantee each other and instead of paying contributions, they contribute to an investment fund or monetary fund.

CONCLUSION

The study of scientific approaches to the essence of Islamic finance and its modern financial instruments, as well as the discovery of the scientific basis of the mechanism and typology of takoful is one of the current issues. The content of

⁶⁰ <http://www.kantakji.com/fiqh/Files/Insurance>

takoful as an economic category in the insurance market and the scientific and theoretical views on its role should be studied in the light of current legislation.

Development and assessment of the current state of the insurance market; substantiate the impact of a single financial instrument on economic development through econometric analysis; The study of the advanced mechanism of introduction of takoful in international practice and the identification of its specific features should be covered.

Analyzed the organizational and legal framework for the introduction of takoful in the economy of Uzbekistan and developed scientifically based proposals and recommendations for the introduction and development of takoful in the economy of Uzbekistan. In Uzbekistan, the use of the takoful instrument is based on the principles of musharaka, mudoraba, murobaha, salam, exception and lease agreements.

Constructive steps should be developed to reflect the priorities of Takoful as a new financial instrument based on best international practices.

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